

ANALYSIS OF ORTHOPEDIC AND SURGICAL METHOD OF REHABILITATION OF PATIENTS WITH COMBINED INJURIES OF THE MAXILLOFACIAL REGION.

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Introduction. Maxillofacial injuries occupy an important place in the general pathology of traumatology and surgery. They can have various forms and degrees of severity, which requires a comprehensive approach to treatment, including surgical intervention and rehabilitation. Combined maxillofacial injuries occur when several anatomical structures are damaged simultaneously, such as the jaws, teeth, soft tissues and bones of the facial skeleton. These injuries can be the result of car accidents, industrial accidents, domestic injuries and violent impacts.

Thus, surgical and orthopedic rehabilitation after combined injuries of the maxillofacial region is a multifaceted process that requires a detailed approach to each case, taking into account the individual characteristics of the patient. It is important to note that a successful outcome of the treatment of combined injuries is possible only with a competent combination of surgical and orthopedic care, as well as with careful adherence to all stages of the rehabilitation process.

Objective of the study. The study is aimed at analyzing effective methods of surgical and orthopedic rehabilitation of patients with combined injuries of the maxillofacial region, evaluating their results and developing recommendations.

Materials and methods. To study the methods of surgical and orthopedic rehabilitation of patients with combined injuries of the maxillofacial region, a comprehensive analysis of clinical data of patients admitted to traumatology and maxillofacial departments of large medical institutions over the past 3 years was conducted. Patients were divided into several groups depending on the type of injury: a group with isolated jaw fractures, a group with combined fractures of the jaw and dentoalveolar system, and a group with combined injuries, including damage to the soft tissues of the face.

The rehabilitation stages included two main periods: early (the time after surgery) and late (long-term recovery). In the early period, the focus was on preventing infectious complications, eliminating swelling and pain, and

restoring the normal position of the jaw. In the late period, more complex rehabilitation measures were carried out, including restoration of the dentition, correction of the bite, and improvement of the functionality of the maxillofacial area.

Results. Of the 85 patients participating in the study, surgical intervention successfully restored the anatomical integrity and functionality of the maxillofacial region in 95% of patients. Complications observed during treatment included infections in the surgical area, as well as impaired bone fusion processes in 5 patients, which required additional surgical correction.

One of the key factors for successful treatment was early restoration of jaw movements using physiotherapy procedures and orthopedic devices. Patients who received such rehabilitation showed the best results in restoring chewing function and normalizing the bite.

In a group of patients requiring dental prostheses, successful implantation of dental structures was performed, which significantly improved the aesthetic and functional results of treatment. Orthopedic prosthetics allowed patients to return to their normal life and ensured normal nutrition, which significantly reduced the risks of malnutrition in the postoperative period.

Rehabilitation in the late period also included the use of hardware methods for bite correction, such as braces, which made it possible to eliminate functional disorders associated with malocclusion and jaw misalignment.

Conclusion. In addition, a significant factor in successful recovery is a multidisciplinary approach, including both traumatologists and maxillofacial surgeons, as well as orthopedists and dentists. In the future, additional research is required to optimize rehabilitation methods and determine the most effective approaches to the treatment of combined injuries of the maxillofacial region.

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